

BUYUK ENSIKLOPEDIK OLIM IBN SINO IJODIDA MA'RIFAT VA JAXOLAT KURASHINING INSON FAROVONLIGINI TA'MINLASH VA SOG'LOM AVLOD TARBIYASIDAGI O'RNI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada Ibn Sino nafaqat buyuk tabib, balki fanning astronomiya, fizika, kimyo, zoologiya, tabiiyot, adabiyot, musiqa sohalarining yaxshi bilishi, u fanning bu sohalarida chuqur fikr yuritgan va betakror asarlar yaratganligi tahlil etilgan. Abu Ali ibn Sinoning yoshlarga nasixati, har bir ishda muloxaza bilan ish yuritishni, o'ziga do'st, sirdosh tanlashda extiyot bo'lishni uqtirishi bayon etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Astronomiya, fizika, kimyo, zoologiya, tabiiyot, adabiyot, musiqa, axloq, qadriyat, axloqiy tarbiyalash, ma'naviyat, ta'lim, tarbiya, ilm-fan.

РОЛЬ БОРЬБЫ ПРОСВЕЩЕНИЯ И НЕНЕВЕДЕНИЯ В ТВОРЧЕСТВЕ ИБН СИНА В ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИИ БЛАГОСОСТОЯНИЯ ЧЕЛОВЕКА

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Аннотация: В данной статье анализируется тот факт, что Ибн Сина был не только великим врачом, но и обладал хорошими познаниями в областях астрономии, физики, химии, зоологии, природы, литературы и музыки. Он глубоко мыслил в этих областях и создал уникальные произведения. Совет Абу

Али ибн Сины молодым людям, что он советует ему быть осторожным в выборе друзей и доверенных лиц, быть осторожным во всем.

Ключевые слова: Астрономия, физика, химия, зоология, природа, литература, музыка, мораль, ценности, нравственное воспитание, духовность, образование, воспитание, наука.

THE ROLE OF THE STRUGGLE OF ENLIGHTENMENT AND NON-IGNORANCE IN THE WORK OF IBN SINA IN ENSURING HUMAN WELL-BEING

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Abstract: This article analyzes the fact that Ibn Sina was not only a great physician, but also had a good knowledge of the fields of astronomy, physics, chemistry, zoology, nature, literature, and music. He thought deeply in these fields and created unique works. Abu Ali ibn Sina's advice to young people, that he advises him to be careful in choosing his friends and confidants, to be careful in everything.

Key words: Astronomy, physics, chemistry, zoology, nature, literature, music, morality, value, moral education, spirituality, education, education, science.

As we know, it is becoming a tradition to give a name to the coming year every year. In the years of independence, a lot of work has been done and is being done on human health and health. In particular, "Healthy Avlod", "Berkamol Avlod", "Healthy mother and child" and many similar concepts were formed.

Our ancestors also did great things in this regard. It is possible to give many opinions about the science of medicine related to the name of Ibn Sinani alone. The fact that the first President Islam Karimov in his book "High Spirituality - Invincible

Power" showed that the word medicine - madati comes from the word Sino makes our hearts dry and full of pride.

Ibn Sina was not only a great physician, but also a good connoisseur of astronomy, physics, chemistry, zoology, nature, literature, and music. He thought deeply in these fields of science and created unique works. Scholars studying Ibn Sina's scientific heritage say that he created more than 450 works in his 57 years of turbulent and turbulent life.

Until the 10th century, in Central Asia, there was no scientifically based teaching about the health-giving effect of physical education exercises on the human body. Abu Ali ibn Sina was the first to create such a doctrine in Central Asia and expressed his thoughts in his famous work called "Kitab ul-gungan fit-tib", i.e. "The Scientific Law of Medicine". This work was published in 1000 It was written in 1024 and finished in 1024. The work consists of 5 volumes and covers all fields of medical science. Also, in this work, the importance of Sino in the health of the human body, his thoughts is also stated.

It is worth noting that Ibn Sina, regardless of the fact that he lived a thousand years ago, believed that as a doctor, it is better to heal the human body and prevent it from getting sick than to treat it after it is sick. . To improve the health of the human body; "The basis of health!" The event is physical education in moderation and at the right time.

It is known that when a person performs physical exercise for a long time, fatigue occurs in his body. Ibn Sina studied such fatigue in depth and divided it into 4 types:

1. Ulcerative fatigue, in which something is felt like touching a wound on the face or bottom of the skin and kadal!
2. Fatigue, in which a person feels as if his body has been pressed and mocked, he feels heat and relaxation in his body.
3. Fatigue from work, in which the body is more tired than usual and seems to be hot.

4 Fatigue, the person experiencing it feels dry and shriveled.

He paid great attention not only to the types of fatigue, but also to its treatment.

Ibn Sina recommended the use of the healing forces of nature to strengthen the body and treat various diseases.

The great thinker's thoughts on improving the health of school-age children's body are of great importance. As we mentioned, physical exercise is the main means of improving the health of the body. He gave a special place to physical exercises in the school program he created.

Ibn Sina, following the path he called for, mastered all the existing scientific developments of his time. This is what it says about it:

From the depths of the black earth to the akvji Zuhul,
I solved one of the problems of the universe.
I understood and untied many difficult knots,
The only thing left unsolved is death.

Before Ibn Sina remained faithful to his opinion, he mastered various fields of science. He had taken the reins of most of his branches. But even if a scientist is knowledgeable and has achieved great success in this field, he considers what he knows to be little compared to the knowledge he needs to know, and even considers his knowledge to be nothing compared to the knowledge he does not know. He encourages people not to be afraid of difficulties in the path of knowledge, to take a bold and steady step. A hero of people, says Ibn Sina, is not afraid of future work and difficulties. He who refuses to mature is the most cowardly of men.

Ibn Sina, in his work, is not shy about the religious fanatics, ignorant people, he is a scholar who does not go beyond prayer, who condemns him when he engages in knowledge and art, science and enlightenment, and he is godless - in dhakri. fights his accusers relentlessly, mockingly laughs at them and writes lines:

These three or four fools who consider themselves wise,
The door is a manifestation of nature.
Be a donkey in these conversations,

If not, they will be called infidels.

Elsewhere he equates the ignorant with the blind who cannot see anything in the world.

"Just as the sun shines invisible to the blind, the world's signs of the right path are invisible to these ignorant people."

Ibn Sina wants to say that it is better to hide your knowledge without speaking in front of such people. He laughs at the rise of some incompetent people to high positions, their unsanctioned and insensitive work.

In his poems, Ibn Sina gives fatherly advice to young people, advises them to be careful in choosing friends and confidants: "Be careful not to tell everyone your secret. Because the word "considerate" is nothing more than being careful. If you keep a secret, it is your prisoner, if it becomes public, you will remain a prisoner of your secret.

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